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PREVALENCE OF PATHOGENIC INTESTINAL PARASITIC INFECTION AMONG RESIDENTS OF FORON JUNCTION, BARKIN LADI LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, PLATEAU STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

*In Nigeria, pathogenic intestinal parasitic infection (PIPI) is one of the neglected tropical diseases of public health importance. The study aimed to ascertain the level of pathogenic intestinal parasitic infections and risk factors among the resident of Foron junction, Barkin Ladi Plateau State. The Objectives of this study include to identify the types of pathogenic intestinal parasites prevalent and to determine prevalence of pathogenic intestinal parasites in the study area among different gender, age groups, social status and risk factors associated in the community. A total of 112 stool samples (64 males and 48 females) were collected from selected residents of the the community and analyzed using parasitological techniques, formalin-ether concentration method.: Forty parasites ova, larva or cysts were encounter with the total prevalence of 40 (27.5%) including *A. lumbricoides* (8.0%), Hookworms spp (6.25%), *Trichuris trichiuria* (4.46%), *E. vermicularis* (5.37%), *H. nana* (2.67%), *G. lamblia* (1.78), *S. stercoralis* (1.78%), *E. histolytica* (2.67%). Males were more infected with the disease (37.5%) than*

females (33.33%). From indications, there is no significant difference in prevalence between males and females ($P < 0.05$). The most prevalent age group was 11-20 years old (40.90%), followed by 20-30 years old (38.09%) while the least prevalent age group was 61-70 years old (28.5%). By occupation, farmers and pupils were the most infected among the residents with 20 (47.61%), pupils 16 (36.36%) and traders 3 (15%). The study concluded that there was a relatively high prevalence of pathogenic intestinal parasitic infection among residents of Foron Junction community and thus recommended improved access to potable water, good toilet facilities, and proper health education on hygiene.

KEYWORDS: Prevalence, Pathogenic, Intestinal Parasitic Infection, Foron Junction, Residents

INTRODUCTION

In developing nations, pathogenic intestinal parasitic infections (PIPI) due to helminths and protozoan are consistently a public health issue (World Health Organization (WHO), 2021; Yonis 2025; Nzeukwu et al., 2025). These infections have common characteristics such as being highly endemic in population with low socioeconomic status (Nzeukwu et al., 2025). Additionally lack of knowledge regarding hygiene practices, such as hand washing, keeping finger nails without trimming, limited access to good health care facilities and potable water (Nzeukwu et al., 2025; Yonis, 2025). These infections caused by human pathogenic intestinal parasite, include large intestinal round worm (*Ascaris lumbricoides*), hookworms (*Ancylostoma duodenale* and *Necator americanus* ‘whipeworm’), pinworm (*Enterobius vermicularis*), *Schistosoma mansoni*, *Hymenolepis nana*, *Taenia spp*, *Giardia lamblia*, *Strongyloides stercoralis*, *Entamoeba histolytica* cyst etc (Yonis, 2025).

Human pathogenic intestinal helminthes are among the most common infection worldwide with 3.5 billion estimated infected persons (Khan et al., 2020,; Gufom et al., 2022,; WHO, 2013). They are otherwise known as Soil-transmitted helminths infections. Over 260 million are pre-school age children, 654 million school age children, 108 million adolescent girls and 138.8 million pregnant and lactating women live in areas where these parasites are intensively transmitted, which requires urgent medical intervention (treatment and prevention). WHO, (2023) cited in (Nzeukwu et al, 2025) population at risk in the West African region are estimated to be at about 350 million. Children as mentioned above especially those living in the tropical regions with warm climatic conditions are mostly affected by pathogenic intestinal parasitic helminths (WHO, 2025).

The most common pathogenic intestinal parasitic helminth of humans throughout Nigeria are *Ascaris lumbricoides*, *Trichuris trichiura*, hookworm spp, *Strongyloides stercoralis* and *Schistosoma mansoni* (Nzeukwu et al., 2025). Many children are at risk of human pathogenic intestinal parasite, due to their poor hygiene most of them make use of pit latrines and often practice open defecation. Although, there are lots of studies on the pathogenic intestinal parasites and associated diseases which have been carried out in Plateau State (Dawet et al., 2022), nothing is documented on the prevalence of the human pathogenic intestinal parasitic infections in the study area, hence the need for this research.

In Nigeria intestinal helminth infection have continue to prevail especially in children because of poor living standard, overcrowding, lack of good health care facilities, poor hygiene, lack of potable water and high level of ignorance on simple healthy behaviours. As reported by Wuso & Onyeabor (2014) (cited in Gufom et al., 2022). WHO, (2008) reported that *Ascaris lumbricoides* infected over one billion people, hookworm spp , 740 million people, *Trichuris trichiura* 79

million people. Furthermore, amoebiasis is reported to cause about 450 million infections per annum in developing countries with an incidence of about 50 million and 10 thousand deaths (Gufom et al., 2022).

This parasitic infection has been reported to contribute to hazardous and major public health issues worldwide associated with high degree of morbidity and mortality. The public health importance of parasitic diseases includes; growth retardation in children, ulcer, internal organs damage, anemia, gross deformation, diarrhea, nutrition deficiency, mal-absorption, weight loss, chloride hyper secretion, dilation of vessels, intestinal obstruction, intestinal perforation, appendicitis, pnueumonitisis, volvalus etc. (Monjur, 2023).

The study is therefore, aimed at investigating the prevalence of human pathogenic intestinal parasitic infection among residents of Foron junction community in Barkin Ladi (Gwol), Local Government Area of Plateau State, North-Central, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- **Study Area**

The study was carried out among residents of Foron junction community in Barkin Ladi Local Government Area of Plateau, Middle Belt, Nigeria. It lies approximately between latitude 9°30N and 9°45N and longitude 8°45E. It is situated 30-40km south of Jos the state capital. It shares boundaries with Riyom to the west, Jos South to the east, part of Mangu to south east and Bokkos to the South. The area has an average elevation of about 2200-1400 meters above sea level (National Population Commission 2000). It is a rural settlement where social amenities like pipe borne water, or borehole water, good health care facilities and latrines are lacking. The residents of Foron junction are generally farmer, miners, civil servants and trader. The sources of their drinking water and household used are from wells and stream. They also lack good toilets, hence, open defecation and urination in nearby bush is a constant practice.

- **Study Population**

The study population comprised of randomly selected adults, young and children between ages 1-70 years,

- **Sample Size**

The sample size was determined by using fisher's formula

$$n = \frac{z^2 Pq}{d^2}$$

Where, n = sample size

d = degree of accuracy (0.05)

z = confidence limit at 95% (1.96)

P = prevalence in the population being tested (7.5%) (Musa et. al., 2015)

q = 1-P

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 0.75 \times 1 - 0.75}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = 103$$

attrition number = 10% = 10.3

Therefore, the sample size that was used is $103 + 10.3 = 113.3$

$$n = 113.3$$

$$n = 112$$

Therefore, a total of 112 stool samples collected from residents of Foron junction community both males and females between ages of 1 and 70 were examined microscopically for the presence or absent of pathogenic intestinal parasitic using standard parasitological techniques -formalin-ether concentration method (Arora & Arora, 2026).

- **Ethical Consideration**

Prior to the study, ethical clearance was sought and received from the appropriate authorities, that is from community leaders. They were briefed on the purpose of the research before sample collection. Oral interview was conducted to obtain the participating individuals' gender, age and occupation.

- **Sample Collection**

Each participant was given one, well labeled and clean transparent sample container to provide his/her stool for the study. Participating individuals were well informed and instructed on how to collect a portion of their stool sample and put into the sample container. The collected stool samples from participants were collected and immediately transported to the Microbiology laboratory of Plateau State Polytechnic, Barkin Ladi for parasitological examination. Samples were collected and analyzed within one hour of sampling time following International best practices (Nzeukwu et al., 2024).

- **Laboratory Analysis**

Formalin-ether concentration method was employed for the sample analysis. Two grams of the stool sample was thoroughly mixed in 10ml of physiological saline. It was then filtered using gauze through a funnel. The filtrate was centrifuged at 2,000 rpm for 2 minutes. The supernatant was discarded. The sediment was re-suspended in 7ml of formalin saline and allowed to stand for 10mins and 3ml of ether was added, shake vigorously to mix. They were centrifuged at 2,000 rpm for 2mins. The supernatant was discarded and the sediment was transferred to clean grease free slide, covered with coverslip and mounted on the microscope stage, was viewed using 10x and 40x objective lenses respectively for the identification of ova or cyst of parasites (Arora & Arora, 2026).

- **Data Analysis**

The data obtained from this study were carefully organized and analyzed using statistical method /chi-square.

RESULTS

Table 1: Prevalence of Pathogenic intestinal parasitic infection in the study area

Parasites	Frequency	Prevalence (%)
Positive samples	40	35.71
Negative samples	72	64.28
Total	112	100

Table 1 presents the prevalence of pathogenic intestinal parasite infection. The prevalence of 40(35.71%) was observed in the study area.

Table 2: Distribution of pathogenic intestinal parasitic infection according to gender in the study area

Sex	Number examined	Number infected	Prevalence (%)
Male	64	24	37.58
Female	58	16	27.58
Total	112	40	35.71

Table 2 shows the level of contamination of pathogenic intestinal parasite of pathogenic intestinal parasitic infection among the gender. The infection rate was higher among males 24(37.58%) while moderate in female 16(27.58%).

Table3: Distribution of pathogenic intestinal parasitic infection according to various age groups in the study area

Age group (years)	Number examined	Number infected	Prevalence (%)
0-10	22	7	31.81
11-20	22	9	40.90
21-30	21	8	38.09
31-40	17	6	35.29
41-50	12	4	33.37
51-60	8	3	37.5
61-70	7	2	28.5
71 and above	3	1	33.33
Total	112	40	35.71

Table 3 presents the relationship between the residents age and prevalence of pathogenic intestinal parasitic infection the highest. Infection was observed in the age groups by those aged 21-30(38.09%), 51-60(37.5%), 31-40(39.29%), 41-50(33.37%), and the lowest infection rate was recorded in adults aged 61-70 years.

Table 4: Pathogenic intestinal parasitic ova, larvae and cyst identified in samples from the study area

Parasites	Number identified	Prevalence
<i>Ascaris lumbricoides</i>	9	8.0
Hookworms	7	6.25
<i>Trichuris trichiuria</i>	5	4.46
<i>Enterobius vermicularis</i>	6	5.37
<i>Schistosoma mansoni</i>	3	2.67
<i>Hymenolepis nana</i>	3	2.67
<i>Giardia lamblia</i>	2	1.78
<i>Strongyloides stercoralis</i>	2	1.28
<i>Entamoeba histolytica</i>	3	2.67
Total	40	35.71

Table 4 captured the frequency and prevalence of individual ova or cyst of parasite identified in the samples from the study area. Nine different intestinal parasites were identified with *Ascaris lumbricoides* has the highest prevalence 9(8.0%) followed by Hookworms 7(6.25%), *Enterobius vermicularis* 6(5.37%), *Trichuris trichiuria* 5 (4.26%) with the lowest in *Giardia lamblia* and *Strongyloides stercoralis* 2 (1.78%).

Table 5: Prevalence of pathogenic intestinal parasitic infection in relation to occupations in the study area

Occupation	Number examined	Number infected	Prevalence
Farmers	42	20	47.61
Traders	20	3	15
Civil servants	6	1	16.6
Pupil	44	16	36.36
Total	112	40	36.71

Table 5 shows that farmers were the most infected with pathogenic intestinal parasite among the different occupation in the study area. Farmers had prevalence of 20(47.61%), followed by pupils 16(36.36%), civil servant 1(16.6%) and trader was lowest with (15%).

Parasitological analysis of stool specimens revealed evidence of infection with pathogenic intestinal parasitic, among 40 of the 112 samples (35.71%) as indicated in table 1. The highest infection rate was observed among males (37.5%) compared to females (27.58%) as shown in Table 2. Distribution of pathogenic intestinal parasitic infection according to various age groups in the study area indicated age 11-20 years rate of infection as 9 (40.90%), followed by those aged 21-30 (38.09%), 31-40. 6 (35.29%) 41-50years 4(33.37%) as shown in table 3. Among the pathogenic intestinal parasitic identified, *Ascaris lumbricoides* was the most prevalent detected in the samples 9(8.09%), this was followed by Hookworm spp, 7(6.25%), *E. vermicularis* 6(5.37%), *S. mansoni* and *H. nana* accounted for 3(2.67%) respectively. The recovered protozoan cyst and trophozoites, *Giardia lamblia* 2(1.78%) and *E. histolytica* 3(2.67%) are as shown in table 4. Table 5 indicated the infection of pathogenic

intestinal parasites in relation to occupation in the study area as follows; Farmers 20(47.61%), pupils 16(36.36%), civil servants 1(16.6%). Traders 3(15.92).

DISCUSSION

The present study set out to ascertain the level and prevalence of different pathogenic intestinal parasitic infections among the residents of Foron junction community, Barkin Ladi Local Government Area, Plateau State. Middle Nigeria. The detection of intestinal pathogenic infection, from faecal samples collected from the participants in the current research is an indicative of faecal contamination of human and animal origin. As in many tropical countries, pathogenic intestinal parasites are widely distributed in Nigeria, not only due to the favorable climatic condition for survival and dissemination of the parasite, but also due to the unsanitary conditions that facilitates faecal pollution of soil, water and contamination of food stuffs (World Health Organization WHO, 2021).

The study found the prevalence of 40(35.7%) pathogenic intestinal parasitic infection among the residence in the study area which is consistent with the previous studies. The findings of this research is in agreement with Dawet et al., (2019), who reported 41.85% in Jos market, Ayubi et al., (2022) recorded 37.3% intestinal parasitic infection among the inhabitants in the rural areas in Joka, Kolkota and Nalanda. Similarly, Azzam & Khalid, (20025) reported prevalence of 46.5% instestinal parasitic infection in Egypt among pre-school and school aged children. Eyayu et al., (2021) observed 52.9% among patients attending Sanja Primary school hospital North-West Ethiopia, Berkel & Shumbe (2019), reported a 42.6% in fruits and vegetables samples contamination due to pathogenic intestinal parasitic infection in Tarcha and South-west Ethiopia, while Wosu & Onyeabor, (2014) reported high prevalence of 75% of pathogenic intestinal in faecal samples among children of both sexes in a tropical rain forest community in South-Eastern Nigeria.

Onyeka et al., (2025) also found the prevalence of 71% among primary school aged children in Plateau Central senatorial district. However, slightly low prevalence of 35.7% possibly due to difference in samples analyses in the study area compared to Dawet et al., 2019, Ayubi et al., (2022), Bekee & Khalid, (2025); Eyagu et al., (2021); Onyeka et al., (2025), this may constitute public health hazards as it could increase unless curtailed early (Gufom, 2022).

The results obtained shows variation in distribution of pathogenic intestinal parasitic infection in relation to gender, age groups, occupation in Foron junction community.

Pathogenic intestinal parasitic infection ova, larva and cyst identified were *A. lumbricoides*, Hookworm spp., *T. trichiuria*, *E. vermicularis*, *S. mansoni*, *H. nana*, *G. lamblia*, *S. stercoralis* and *E. histolytica*. The most common prevalent is *A. lumbricoides* as 9(8.08). Hookworm spp. 7(6.25%), *E. vermicularis* 6(5.37%), *T. trichuria* 5(4.46%), *S. mansoni*, *H. nana* and *E. histolytica* had 3(2.67%) while *G. lamblia* and *S. stercoralis* has 2(1.7%). This, is in line with the findings of Eyagu et al., (2025) who reported a prevalence of *E. histolytica* (21.5%) Hookworms species (13.5%), *S. mansoni* 1(9.4%), *G. lamblia* 9.2%. The infection rate was slightly higher in males (37.5%) than females (27.58%) in the study area, possibly due to occupational or behavioural factors which aligns with the findings of Nock et al., (2019) who reported higher prevalence in males (63.6%) compared to females in their research on geohelminths infections of some groups of school children in Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria. The infection rate in the age group showed that 11-20 had the highest prevalence (40.90%), 21-30 (38.09%), 51-60 (37.5%), 31-40 (35.29%), 41-50 (33.37%), with lowest of (28.5%) among age group of 61-70years.

Infections in relation to occupations indicated that farmers had 20(47.6%) which was the highest followed by pupils/students 17(38.63%), Traders 3(1%), while civil servants was 0(0%). The findings are supported by the studies carried out on humans' intestinal parasitic infection in rural areas of Joka, Kolhata and Nalanda (Ayubi et al., 2022). Melkonmen et al., (2022) also reported similar pattern in Ethiopia, where adults working in farms had significantly higher worms' infections than children. Several factors might have contributed to farmers and pupils having higher prevalence of pathogenic intestinal parasitic infections in Foron junction community, Plateau State, Middle Belt Nigeria to include occupational exposure, poor sanitation and hygiene, eating habits, limited health education and socioeconomic factors.

Regarding species prevalence, *Ascaris lumbricoides* was the most frequency detected pathogenic intestine parasites among the participants in Foron junction. In the epidemiological profile, was observed with *Ascaris lumbricoides* infections (8%) predominating over Hookworms spp *lumbricoides*, Hookworms spp and *Trichuris trichiuria* infections has been documented by other researchers (Ndong Ngomo et al., 2025). In contrast in Cameroon, infection with *Ascaris lumbricoides* (29.8%), hookworms (29.4%) and *Trichuris trichiuris* (10.7%) were more prevalent among the population (Koizeniewski et al., 2021 cited in Bdong Ngomo, 2025).

- **Gender**

In this, research, males were found to be more infected as 24 (37.58%) compared to females who had 16(27.58%) in the study area. These findings on the prevalence of pathogenic intestinal parasitic infections in males being higher than females align with some similar studies. For instance a study in Zaria, Kaduna State by Nock et al, (2019) who reported higher prevalence in males (63.6%) compared to female in their each on geohelminths of some groups of school children Ali et al., (2023) reported similar prevalence of 58.9% in males and 29.3% in females in Akwanga, Nassarawa State, Nigeria.

- **Age**

In age, the high prevalence of these infections among participants aged 11-20 years (40.90%), 21-30 years (38.09%), 51-60 years (37.5%), 31-40 years (35.29%), 41-50 years (33.37%), 71 & above years (33.33%), 0-10 years (31.81%), and 61-70 years (28.5%). The factors contributed to the high prevalence of intestinal parasitic infections amongst participants in Foron junction community is likely due to poor sanitation inadequate water supply or lack of access to clean latrine, health facility, poor hygiene practices, poor food handling, open defecation and waste disposal, Ogwezzy et al., 2024, Yosnis, 2025)

- **Occupation**

Infections with the pathogenic intestinal parasites in relations to occupations showed that farmer had 20(47.6%) which was the highest followed by pupils 16(36.6%), trades 3(15%), and civil servant had 1(16%). This indicates that farmers and pupils have higher prevalence rates of pathogenic intestinal parasitic infection compared to traders and civil servants. The findings in this study are supported by the studies carried out on human intestinal parasitic infections in rural areas of Joka Kolhata and Nalanda (Ayubi et al, 2022). Melkonmen et al (2022) also reported similar pattern in Ethiopia where adults working in farms had a significantly higher worm's infection than in children. Several factors might have contributed to farmers and pupils having higher prevalence of pathogenic intestinal infections among residents of Foron junction community to include occupational exposure, poor sanitation and hygiene, limited health education, eating habits, lack of access safe water, open defecation. Socio-economic factors and personal hygiene practices also

plays a very crucial role in determining the risk factors of infection and its progression into serious health concerns, they affect individuals' overall wellbeing and health status (Yonis, 2025).

Socioeconomic factors and personal hygiene practices plays a very crucial role in determining the risk factors of infection and its progression into serious health concerns. They affect individuals' overall wellbeing and health status (Yonis, 2025). Lower income families often face challenges in maintaining living condition and access to clean water regularly, which increases the likelihood of parasitic transmission among the community. Furthermore, health education program should be emphasized. Proper hygiene practices among the residents with local health authorities while engaging the people to reinforce hygiene practices in the community.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion the study reveals a high prevalence of pathogenic intestinal parasitic infection in Foron junction community, Plateau State, Nigeria, affecting male and female farmers, traders, Pupils, Civil servants as well as various age groups due to poor sanitation hygiene open defecation, lack health facilities and limited health education.

• Recommendations

A proper implementation of WASH programs is recommended to improve sanitation and hygiene infrastructure. Also, there is the need promote proper waste disposal among residents as well regular deworming programs, and mass screening of pathogenic intestinal parasite.

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